

Public Transport Harassment, Resilience and Perceived Safety among Female Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 05, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Harassment, Resilience, Perceived Safety, Public Transport</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7405495</p>	<p><i>Female students of the university are reluctant to take public transportation due to experiencing public transport harassment. The main aim of the study was to find out the relationship between public transport harassment, resilience, and perceived safety in female students. The present study was conducted using cross-sectional research design. Purposive sampling was used to select the sample of 200 female students with the age range of 16-27 years old. Scales which are used in the study were: The sexual Harassment Experience Questionnaire (SHEQ) developed by Kamal and Tariq in 1998. Psychological resilience scale was developed by Windle et al. in 2008. The perceived safety scale was developed by Syropoulos in 2018. It was concluded that public transport harassment negatively correlates with perceived safety and resilience among female students. The results also revealed that resilience partially mediates between harassment and perceived safety.</i></p>

Introduction

Sexual harassment is a worldwide phenomenon that is increasing every day. Sexual harassment is defined as any unwanted sexual attention including lewd comments, ogling, sexual invitations, rape, unwanted sexual touch, staring, and being followed or photographed by someone. The behaviors involved may range from mild to serious (Anwar et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2022).

Types of Harassment

According to Adhikari et al. (2020) Sexual harassment is divided into three forms: verbal, nonverbal, and physical. Verbal harassment includes making sexual remarks about a person's clothing or physique asking intimate questions about sexual lives, preferences, desires, or history, and persistently "asking out" a person who is not interested, telling sexual jokes or comments; are all instances of verbal forms of sexual harassment. Nonverbal types of sexual harassment include whistling, staring, and leering. Displaying sexually suggestive imagery; making facial expressions such as winking, throwing kisses, presenting personal presents of a sexual nature, and making sexual gestures with hands or by body movements. Physical harassment includes touching and rubbing hanging around, getting close, or brushing up against someone; touching a person's body, hair, or clothes including massage around the neck and shoulders.

Public Transport Harassment

Public transport harassment refers to any action or speech between strangers in public places that are rude, unpleasant, threatening, or harassing, motivated by gender, sexual orientation, or gender expression (Gardner et al., 2017). Female students of the university are reluctant to take public transportation due to experiencing public transport harassment. Furthermore, the majority of females are subjected to the misbehavior of drivers and co-passengers. To prevent unfavorable situations, female passengers prefer not to take public transportation (Sumbal, 2022). According to a study by Aycok et al. (2019) women in male-dominated occupations are more likely to be sexually harassed, and these experiences raise job turnover intentions and withdrawal from work. Sexual harassment not only occurs in their domains but also contributes to their educational and professional environments.

Prevalence of Harassment

The overall prevalence of sexual harassment was found to be 79.6% in a sample of 369 female students. It was found that 61.2% of female students experienced verbal harassment and 34.6% experienced nonverbal harassment. Physical harassment (67.1) % was found to be a more prominent type of harassment. After experiencing sexual harassment 44.6% of female students rebuked the harasser, 29.1% kept silent and 9% reacted in different ways. According to 69.2%, female student overcrowding was the main reason for sexual harassment, 36.8% did not use any precautions for sexual harassment and 32.6% avoided going alone at night. All these findings indicate a high prevalence of sexual harassment among female students (Mishra & Lamichanne, 2018).

Resilience in Women to Deal with Harassment

Resilience is defined as the ability to recover despite adversity, looking ahead through a dynamic process of adaptation supported by a deeper understanding of oneself and impacted by personal qualities, family, and societal resources. It takes the form of adaptable attitudes and actions that allows one to stay psychologically healthy or even predict personal improvement in the face of adverse life situations (Sisto et al., 2019). Resilience indicates good coping techniques in reaction to unfavorable harassment experiences. Female adolescents who reported low resilience had greater sexual harassment. It suggests that adolescents with a higher level of resilience may be better at avoiding sexual harassment. It could also be related to differences in networks and friendship groups, such as the fact that highly resilient young women belong to friendship groups with more supportive norms (Mitchell & Stulhofer, 2021; Ghani et al., 2022).

Resilience as a Process of Purifying Spirit

According to female victims of sexual harassment, resilience is a process of purifying the spirit and freeing oneself of the negative effects of sexual harassment. They stressed the need of working through sorrow, taking care of oneself, letting go of bad mindsets, creating healthy interpersonal and spiritual relationships, and forgiving oneself and others, among other things. It became clear that their journey had led them to new identities. Despite their sexual harassment experiences, they developed a new self-image that included viewing themselves as strong women who can survive, adapt to change, and build good relationships (Newsom & Myers-Bowman, 2017).

Harassment and Perceived Safety

The experience of "the risk of becoming a crime victim and disturbance of public order" is referred to as perceived safety. Both the possibility of being a victim and the reality of becoming a victim may have an equal influence on people's lives (Jansson, 2019). Women's increased worry about personal safety can have an impact on their everyday mobility by limiting their mobility options and behaviors in terms of location, time, and mode (Hidayati et al., 2020).

Women who can afford private transportation and choose to utilize it for reasons other than commuting have no impact of harassment. Some women pay for private transportation to avoid harassment (Wilder, 2018).

Economic Impact of Harassment

The International Labour Organization (ILO) estimates that only 5% of Pakistan's women have paid jobs due to a lack of transportation, and that "women workers spend nearly half of their salaries on transportation, while their male counterparts spend only 5%." (Panjwani, 2018). Women in Pakistan suffer a variety of obstacles, including safety, harassment, barriers to work and education, social stigma, poor accessibility, and little allocated space in buses and stations. Unwanted male attention and a sense of insecurity on public transportation were the most important elements in women's decision to switch to more expensive private means, forcing them to walk long distances (Malik et al., 2020; Ahmad et al., 2022).

Environment Factors and Perceived Safety

Females are anxious about traveling on both public transport and ridesharing service at night. When it comes to safety 78% of people preferred to travel on Uber instead of a public bus because they feel safer. The majority of the participants reported that the public bus was not safe enough and 59% of people preferred using Uber over a public bus (Burn, 2019). Women tend to use mobile phones and headphones as a defense mechanism against their anxiety while waiting at a bus stop. Women are aware of their surroundings and pretend to be more confident while waiting. Safety perception from family and friends has an influence on a women personal safety while waiting at the stop (Chowdhury & Wee, 2020).

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to explore the relationship between harassment, resilience, and the perceived safety of graduate and undergraduate students.

Methodology

Research Design

In the present research, cross-sectional research design was used

Sample

The sample was comprised of 100 undergraduate and 100 graduate (N=200) females. Data was gathered from different educational institutes in Lahore. Undergraduate and graduate female students were recruited as participants using the purposive sampling approach. Female undergraduate and graduate students were included in the study. Married and unmarried female students of age between 17-27 years were included. Only Female

students using public transport were included in this research. Participants who did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded from the study.

Measures

A demographic form, Perceived Safety Scale, Psychological Resilience Scale, and Sexual Harassment Experience Questionnaire were used in this research to find out public transport harassment, resilience, and perceived safety in female students.

Sexual Harassment Experience Questionnaire

Kamal and Tariq (1997) developed a scale named as Sexual Harassment Experience Questionnaire which measures the sexual harassment experiences of women in Pakistan. This scale contains 35 items. The response options included (1) Never (2) once (3) a few times and (4) very frequent on this scale. The scale has psychometric properties which are significant and can be used for measuring harassment. The scale has a reliability of .94 by using Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

Psychological Resilience Scale

The psychological Resilience Scale was developed by (Windle et al.,2008). It consists of 19 items that represent the constructs of self-esteem, interpersonal control, and personal competence. This scale is of Likert type ranging from 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree. The reliability of the final scale is .83. Cronbach's alpha was 0.80 for interpersonal control, 0.80 for the personal competence dimension, and 0.84 for self-esteem before data reduction. The higher score indicates a higher level of resilience.

Perceived Safety Scale

The perceived Safety Scale was developed by (Syropoulos,2018). This scale consists of 25 items on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (very strongly disagree) to 7 (very strongly agree). The reliability of the P-SAFE scale was evaluated using a reliability test (Cronbach's alpha). Overall, the complete scale's reliability is .968. Cronbach's alpha for Fear of Crime is .938, for Feeling Safe is .824 and for Safety Confidence is .407).

Ethical Considerations

Ethics that are taken into consideration were as followed:

- Prior permission from the authors was obtained for the use of scales.
- Participants were first told about the study's purpose before voluntarily participating in the research.
- All information was obtained with the participants' consent and agreement. The participants were told that all information obtained from them would be kept confidential and that no information relating to them would be used for reasons other than academic and empirical research, ensuring that confidentiality would not be violated.
- The participants were given the option to withdraw at any moment.

Results

The chapter on results will present the demographic characteristics of the sample, the reliability of the scales, and the statistical analysis of the study.

Variables	F	%
Education		
Undergraduate	100	50.0
Graduate	100	50.0
Socio economic status		
Middle class	180	90.0
Upper class	20	10.0
Modes of transport		
Chingchi	8	4.0
Auto	46	23.0
Van	87	43.5
Metro bus/speedo	26	13.0
Uber	33	16.5
Average hr. in transport		
One hour	160	80.0
two hour	33	16.5
>2 hours	7	3.5

As shown in Table 1, all participants were undergraduates and Graduate students. Only twenty-seven percent of girls were married and twenty percent belongs to upper middle-class socio-economic status. In the modes of transport, eighty-seven percent of participants used vans and only forty-six percent of girls used autos. Most participants who use Uber were thirty-three percent and belong to the upper middle class. the table also shows that sixty participants spent one hour on public transport and only eight percent were found to spend more than two hours.

Table 2
Correlation among harassment, resilience and perceived safety

Variables	1	2	3
Harassment	–	.082	-.65**
Resilience	–	–	-.140*
Perceived safety	–	–	–

Note: **p<.05, ***p<.01

Table results revealed a significant negative relationship between harassment and resilience ($r=-.140^*$, $p<.01$) and a significant negative relationship between harassment with perceived safety ($r=-.65^{**}$, $p<.05$).

Table 3
Linear regression of harassment as a predictor of perceived safety

Variable	perceived safety		
BSEB	β		
Harassment	-1.26	7.35	-.34
R ²			.43
F			75.19

Note. **p<.01

The results show that harassment negatively predicts perceived safety among female students ($\beta= -.34$, $p<0.1$) which explained 50% variance.

Table 4
Multiple Regression Analysis for Predicting psychological resilience and perceived safety from sexual harassment in female students (N=200)

Model	Harassment female students (N=200)		
	B	SE	B
Constant	58.82	3.5	
Resilience	-.33	.02	-.64
Perceived safety	-.00	.04	-.00
R ²	.42		
F	72.9		

Note: R²= Adjusted R square, B= unstandardized coefficients= Standard error β =standard beta coefficient.

It was hypothesized that the more they experience public transport harassment the less will be resilience and perceived safety in female students. To check the hypothesis, public transport harassment, resilience, and perceived safety are put into multiple regression analysis. Harassment was taken as a dependent variable and perceived safety and resilience were taken as an independent variable. Resilience and perceived safety explain the difference ($F=72.9$, $P=0.00$) that supports the model. Results revealed that harassment negatively predicts resilience and is perceived in female students.

Table 5
Mean comparison of undergraduate and graduate students for measuring perceived safety and resilience. (N=200)

Variables	Undergraduate		Graduate		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	95% of CI
	n =100		n =100				
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
<i>M</i>							
<i>SD</i>							

Perceived safety	46.29	37.32	42.12	34.63	0.81	0.41	-5.87	14.21
Resilience	62.24	20.67	62.37	20.96	-0.04	0.96	-5.93	5.67

Note: M = Mean, SD = St. Deviation

It was hypothesized that graduate students have more resilience and perceived safety than undergraduate students. An Independent sample t-test was used to measure differences. The findings revealed that there would be significant differences in resilience and perceived safety among graduate and undergraduate students. Table results revealed significant mean differences between graduate and undergraduate students. Findings showed that graduate students showed higher scores in resilience ($M = 62.37$, $SD = 20.96$) and low scores in perceived safety ($M = 42.12$, $SD = 34.63$) than undergraduate students. The findings also indicate that undergraduate students have scored high in perceived safety ($M = 46.29$, $SD = 37.32$) than graduate students.

Figure 6

Multiple Regression on Resilience as Mediator between Sexual Harassment and Perceived Safety among Female Students

It is hypothesized that resilience will mediate between harassment and perceived safety among graduate and undergraduate students. To check the hypothesis, linear and multiple regression were used in three steps. In the first step, the outcome variable is regressed on the predictor harassment to establish that there is an effect to mediate resilience (path c) with perceived safety outcomes score as $c = 1.275$, ($Se_c = .105$, $p = 0.00$). In the second step, resilience is regressed on the predictor variable harassment to establish (path a) $a = .093$, ($Se_a = .080$, $p = 0.00$). In the last step the perceived safety is regressed on both the predictor and mediator (path b and c') score as $b = -.151$, ($Se_b = .093$, $p = 0.00$) $c' = -1.261$, ($Se_{c'} = .105$, $p = .00$). Resilience is partial mediate between harassment and perceived safety as $c' < c$ that is mean harassment is one of the reasons of perceived safety and resilience.

Discussion

The purpose of the study was to find out the relationship between harassment, resilience, and perceived safety in female students. For this purpose extensive study of previous literature was done. Different hypotheses were formulated and tested.

In the current study first hypothesis formulated and tested was "Public transport harassment would be negatively correlated with resilience and perceived safety among students". The findings revealed that harassment is negatively correlated with resilience and perceived safety. The findings are consistent with previous research done by Teodora (2015) which revealed that harassment negatively and significantly correlates with resilience means those higher scores of resilience correlate with the low score of

harassment. Sexual victimization in transportation situations appears to be linked to stated levels of perceived safety in these circumstances, independent of city or nation context (Ceccato & Sideris, 2021).

The second hypothesis that was formulated and tested was “there will be a negative relationship between harassment and perceived safety. The results of the present study showed that harassment is negatively correlated with perceived safety. The findings are consistent with previous research which showed that harassment was negatively associated with perceived safety in crowded public places and perceived safety in isolated public places (Davidson et al., 2016).

The third hypothesis that was formulated and tested was “harassment would negatively predict perceived safety among students”. The results of the present study showed that harassment negatively predicts perceived safety among students. The findings are consistent with previous research was done by McGuire et al. (2010) which revealed that sexual harassment was significantly related to perceived safety, whereas intolerance was related to increased perceived safety from sexual harassment. Sexual harassment was found to be significantly related to females' perceived safety.

The fourth hypothesis that was formulated and tested was “the more the experience of public transport harassment, the less will be resilience and perceived safety in female students. The findings are consistent with previous research done by Laura (2020) Experiences of harassment were substantially associated with a lower perception of safety in general and in crowded places in particular. Sideris (2020) showed the impact of harassment on women's travel behavior, which revealed that women took cautious measures in reaction to sexual harassment in public areas. Female students with low resilience experienced more sexual harassment. It implies that students with greater levels of resilience may be better able to avoid sexual harassment (Mitchell & Stulhofer, 2021).

The fifth hypothesis that was formulated and tested was “Graduate students have more resilience and perceived safety than undergraduate students. The findings revealed that there are significant differences in resilience and perceived safety among graduate and undergraduate students. Graduate students have more resilience than undergraduate students. The findings are consistent with the literature, which revealed that depending on their academic year and life experience, students conceptualized resilience differently. The main characteristics associated with resilience in graduate and undergraduate students were found to be keeping perspective, maintaining health, and creating support systems. Students that are resilient get significant rewards while dealing with hardship (Holdsworth et al., 2017). The results are similar to the findings of the research done by Maier and Deprince (2019) that sense of safety rises in students if they believe there are enough safety precautions in place. High intolerance for sexual harassment and low sexual harassment experience were significantly linked with higher perceived safety from sexual harassment in females. The result of research by Verma et al. (2020) also showed that women with greater educational qualifications regard themselves as safer in buses than those with lesser educational qualifications.

The sixth hypothesis that was formulated and tested was “Resilience would mediate the relationship between harassment and perceived safety. The results showed that resilience is a partial mediator between harassment and perceived safety as that is mean harassment is one of the reasons for perceived safety and resilience. The findings are consistent with previous research was done by Pedro et al. (2019) that resilience has a partial mediating role with harassment. Resilience may reduce discomfort at all degrees of adversity, regardless of how the exposed person perceives the level. Resilient people are more adjusted to this psychological stressor. Mediating roles when present is most significant at lower levels of harassment and diminishes at larger levels. Another study conducted by Lin et al. (2022) had been demonstrated that resilience protects against bullying and harassment. Higher resilience levels, in particular, provide the most protection for victims of harassment. Early efforts to decrease the detrimental impacts of bullying victimization may begin with developing adolescent resilience. Sideris (2020) showed the impact of harassment on women's travel behavior, which revealed that women took cautious measures in reaction to sexual harassment in public areas.

Conclusion

This research investigated the relationship between public transport harassment, resilience, and perceived safety among females. It also aimed to study the mediating role of resilience between perceived safety and harassment. It also aimed to explore significant statistical differences in resilience and perceived safety among graduate and undergraduate students. Based on this, it was concluded that public transport harassment negatively correlated with resilience and perceived safety among female students. It was concluded that harassment positively predicts resilience and perceived safety in female students. According to the findings, resilience is partially a mediator between harassment and perceived safety. There were very few researches relevant to the present study so the present study can provide the basis for future studies.

Limitations

There was limited time for data collection. It was difficult to gather many respondents' experiences since they were all hesitant to say anything. The sample size was limited to female university students. The drawbacks of

this study can be solved by a larger sample and a varied population. As a result, future research will be more generalizable and representative of the population.

Suggestions

Additional time should be spent on the research so that more details may be discovered. Qualitative research, in addition to quantitative research, should be performed to obtain more accurate data. The sample was chosen via a survey approach, and it included exclusively female students. To enhance generalization, the sample could be taken from working women. More study is needed to investigate the significant influence of resilience and perception on public transportation harassment faced by female students. Further study in such topics will be beneficial in providing different viewpoints for a better understanding of harassment in women's travel behavior with public transportation in the future.

Acknowledgment

The researchers would like to thank all of the female students using public transport for participating in this study and sharing their experiences with us.

References

- Adhikari, R., Sah, B., Subedi, P., Panthi, L., Thapaliya, P., & Baniya, A. (2020). Sexual harassment in public transport and its coping strategies among bachelor students: A cross sectional study. *Journal of Karnali Academy of Health Sciences*, 3(3), 3-9.
- Afek, A., Ben-Avraham, R., Davidov, A., Berezin Cohen, N., Ben Yehuda, A., Gilboa, Y., & Nahum, M. (2021). Psychological resilience, mental health, and inhibitory control among youth and young adults under stress. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11(6), Article e11:60858824. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.608588>
- Anwar, F., Osterman, K., & Bjorkqvist, K. (2020). Risk factors for sexual harassment in public places. *Technium Social Scences journal*, 8, 329-343.
- Ahmad, S., Islam, M., Zada, M., Khattak, A., Ullah, R., Han, H., ... & Araya-Castillo, L. (2022). The Influence of Decision Making on Social Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities: A Case Study of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(2), 858.
- Burn, S. M. (2019). The psychology of sexual harassment. *Teaching of Psychology*, 46(1), 96-103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628318816183>
- Ceccato, V., & Loukaitou-Sideris, A. (2022). Fear of sexual harassment and its impact on safety perceptions in transit environments: a global perspective. *Violence against women*, 28(1), 26-48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10778012211992874>
- Chowdhury, S., & Van Wee, B. (2020). Examining women's perception of safety during waiting times at public transport terminals. *Transport policy*, 94, 102-108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2020.05.009>
- Davidson, M. Meghan, Michael S. Butchko, Krista Robbins, Lindsey W. Sherd, and Sarah J. Gervais. "The mediating role of perceived safety on street harassment and anxiety." *Psychology of Violence* 6, no. 4 (2016): 553-561. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0039970>
- García-Izquierdo, M., Meseguer-de-Pedro, M., Soler-Sánchez, M. I., & Fernández-Valera, M. M. (2019). The role of resilience between workplace bullying and health: A mediational analysis. *Revista de Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones*, 35(3), 177-182. <https://doi.org/10.5093/jwop2019a16>
- Gardner, N., Cui, J., & Coiacetto, E. (2017). Harassment on public transport and its impacts on women's travel behaviour. *Australian Planner*, 54(1), 8-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07293682.2017.1299189>
- Ghani, B., Zada, M., Memon, K. R., Ullah, R., Khattak, A., Han, H., ... & Araya-Castillo, L. (2022). Challenges and Strategies for Employee Retention in the Hospitality Industry: A Review. *Sustainability*, 14(5), 2885.
- Hidayati, I., Tan, W., & Yamu, C. (2020). How gender differences and perceptions of safety shape urban mobility in Southeast Asia. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 73, 155-173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2020.06.014>
- Jansson, C. (2019). Factors important to street users' perceived safety on a main street.
- Khan, N. U., Zada, M., Ullah, A., Khattak, A., Han, H., Ariza-Montes, A., & Araya-Castilo, L. (2022). Servant Leadership and Followers Prosocial Rule-Breaking: The Mediating Role of Public Service Motivation. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13.
- Maier, S. L., & DePrince, B. T. (2020). College students' fear of crime and perception of safety: The influence of personal and university prevention measures. *Journal of criminal justice education*, 31(1), 63-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511253.2019.1656757>
- Mishra, D., & Lamichhane, J. (2018). Experience of sexual harassment in public transport among female health science students: A cross sectional study of Kathmandu, Nepal. *Journal of Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Sciences*, 4(1), 20-32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3126/jmmihs.v4i1.21134>

- Mitchell, K., & Štulhofer, A. (2021). Online sexual harassment and negative mood in Croatian female adolescents. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry, 30*(2), 225-231. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-020-01506-7>
- Malik, B. Z., ur Rehman, Z., Khan, A. H., & Akram, W. (2020). Women's mobility via bus rapid transit: experiential patterns and challenges in Lahore. *Journal of Transport & Health, 17*, 100834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2020.100834>
- Newsom, K., & Myers-Bowman, K. (2017). "I am not a victim. I am a survivor": Resilience as a journey for female survivors of child sexual abuse. *Journal of child sexual abuse, 26*(8), 927-947. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10538712.2017.1360425>
- S. T. Cynthia, M. Majumder, A. Tabassum, N. N. Khanom, R. Amin Tuhin and A. K. Das, "Security Concerns of Ridesharing Services in Bangladesh," 2019 2nd International Conference on Applied Information Technology and Innovation (ICAITI), 2019, pp. 44-50. doi:10.1109/ICAITI48442.2019.8982128.
- Sisto, A., Vicinanza, F., Campanozzi, L. L., Ricci, G., Tartaglino, D., & Tambone, V. (2019). Towards a transversal definition of psychological resilience: a literature review. *Medicina, 55*(11), 745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina55110745> STOCKHOLM, SVERIGE. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1354309/FULLTEXT01>.
- Sumbal, Sumbal, Harassment of Women in University and Public Transport (March 31, 2022). *European Scientific Journal, 18*(10), 39- 2022. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2022>.
- Teodora, M. C. (2015). Understanding resilience through its associated concepts. *Journal of Education Research and Behavioural Sciences, 4*(8), 241-245. <http://www.apexjournal.org>
- Turner, M., Scott-Young, C. M., & Holdsworth, S. (2017). Promoting wellbeing at university: the role of resilience for students of the built environment. *Construction management and economics, 35*(11-12), 707-718. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2017.1353698>

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